

THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUFISM IN THE MIDDLE AGES

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The genesis of Sufism and the stages of its development, views on the formation of the theoretical system, and the variety of studies indicate that Sufism is a unique complex research object. Shows that the discussions have expanded on various issues. Aziziddin Nasafi in his work "Bayan al-Tanzil" states that at the beginning of Sufism, "zuhd" appeared in the form of "dieting". According to him, Hasan Basri and Fuzayl Iyaz added "Huzn" "sadness" to zuhd. Rabia Adaviya and Zunnun Misri performed "Love". Shaiqi Balkhi and his students promoted Tawakkul. Each of these views and ideas caused various arguments and debates in its own way. This, on the one hand, paved the way for the origin of various currents and leeches in Sufism, and created the foundation for the formation of silsilas, sects, and even mystical schools. The division of Sufis into different sects created a uniqueness in Sufism even in the field of pilgrimage. In this regard, Western scientists have taken the interest in the analysis of Sufi ideas and the views of great Sufis to a new level in their research.

In Sufism, divine love is considered as the main means of attaining the truth. In Sufism, divine love is also considered as a person's love for God and love for the servant of the Truth. The fact that a person is in the eyes of the Truth is also reflected in the purity and strength of a person's faith, a gift given to him for his good deeds during his life or a test given to him. Along with the emergence of love in him for the creations of the truth, for the whole being, it also leads to an increase in respect, reverence and love for the human race. A person's worth shows the essence of humanity. His morals become beautiful, and he also has a beautiful effect on the environment.

Discussions of the word, Sufism and religious-philosophical nature that continued in the Middle Ages paved the way for the development of views on Sufism. Sufism, which has a unique place among Islamic sciences, absorbed the noble ideas of Islam, reflected the people's aspirations for freedom, justice, gentleness, and mutual unity, manifested itself as a spiritual phenomenon in the Middle Ages.

7th century and spread to many countries of Asia, Africa and Europe, presented to the peoples of these regions not only a new faith, but also a new way of life, new social and human relations, along with moral values, standards and criteria of humanity. The teachings of Sufism, which was formed on the

basis of the teachings of Islam and relied on the principles of humanity, promoted the virtues of putting a person's identity above all material goods, whims, and pleasures of the world, and secondly, following the culture of compromise in relations with people. Arab scientist Abdul Qadir Isa says that there was no need for Sufism in the first centuries of Islam, because it was a time of pious and pious people who devoted themselves completely to God. At the same time, the propagation of Islam played an important role in its spread, its penetration into many countries, its absorption into the traditions and values of peoples, and its transformation into a way of thinking and lifestyle, as well as the development of Sufism as an ideological source, like other teachings.

From the beginning of the Middle Ages, Hakim Termizi's effort to study the theoretical issues of Sufism laid the groundwork for further improvement of Sufism at the level of teaching. Abu Bakr Kalabadi and Mustamli Bukharis played a special role in the formation of Movarounnahr schools of Sufism and the systematization of Sufism. They completed the systematization of Sufism, started by Hakim Termizi. Sufi views in the works of Abu Bakr Kalabadi "At-Ta'arruf li mazhab ahl al-tasawuf", "Bahrul-fawaid", Mustamli Bukhari "Sharh at-Ta'arruf li mazhab ahl at-tasawuf", Hujviri's "Kashf ul-mahjub" the history, the expression of the theoretical issues of Sufism in a broad and understandable language became important in the comprehensive study of Sufism teachings of its time and the following period. Of course, an opportunity has been created for this Sufism to become a doctrine that can be studied, explained, and taught.

Formation and development of Sufism at the level of doctrine in a difficult period was not easy. In all times, there were sects and doctrines opposing Sufism, just as there were defenders of Sufism. In the Middle Ages, social consciousness influenced the development of philosophical and mystical thought, and Sufism, like philosophy, kalam and other teachings, gained its influence and place because it supported superstition in its own way. It was deeply embedded in the cultural and spiritual life of the society with the encouragement to reach the vassal of God, stay away from all desires, purify the heart, look inside, work honestly, and pursue a profession.

The development of Sufism in different directions from the beginning of the Middle Ages can be imagined as follows:

1. In the 9th-11th centuries, deepening of the foundations of monotheism, the concepts of fano (absence) and baqa (existence), unity and kasrat, assimilation to God (being a source) were studied;

2. From the middle of the 13th century, the intellectual-mental direction "vahdatul-vujud" was leading;

3. In the 14th-15th centuries, the mystical, religious-philosophical issues of Sufism, and the theoretical problems of achieving knowledge of the truth began to be studied.

In this regard, researcher I.Usmanov analyzes the past periods of Sufism and emphasizes that they can be divided into several stages. According to him, the teachings of Sufism cover such topics as the human heart, his psyche, self-cultivation, the perfect person, high spirituality, beautiful manners, and spiritual perfection. The periods from the emergence of Sufism to the present can be theoretically divided into the following stages:

- period of asceticism;
- the period of mysticism;
- the era of unity and prosperity;
- the era of sects;
- modern mysticism.

The 7th-8th centuries were considered the period of "Zuhd" and the characteristics of the ascetics, their obedient prayers, turning away from worldly possessions, and their ascetic way of life, finding God's approval, attaining the happiness of two worlds, and getting rid of sufferings, were considered important. It was distinguished from other stages of Sufism by the fact that it did not have the concepts of knowing God and reaching his presence. Fear and hope were the dominant emotions and concepts in the lives of hermits. The hermits of this period were dominated by the concept of asceticism based on "fear". But in the 8th century, the introduction of new concepts related to the famous ascetic woman Rabiya al-Adawiya (d. 135/752) of the Basra school of Sufism, that is, the concept of divine love, caused the expansion of thoughts and views, as we mentioned above. The desire to find God's love led to the origin of the concepts of divine love. The great Sufism theorist of the 10th century, Abu Bakr Kalabadi from Bukhara, expressed his thoughts on this issue in "at-Ta'arruf" and said that "man is in a state between fear and hope". He explains that fear is the fear of God's wrath, that is, the feeling of being afraid of his wrath, while hope is the hope of attaining his pleasure.

However, among some Sufism scholars, there are views that asceticism developed separately from Sufism. In this respect, researchers believe that asceticism developed as a unique direction rather than as the starting point of Sufism. According to them, if Sufism is the next stage of asceticism, then

asceticism should have disappeared during the period when Sufism developed. In the sources, it is noted that during the Mamluk era, most of the Egyptian jurists and scholars were not Sufis, but ascetics. Mustafa al-'Azizi, who died in 1157/1744, is also mentioned as a "hermit" in the work "Ajo'ib al-asor". However, he worked during the Ottoman period, when Sufism reached its highest position. The early Sufis also mentioned influential followers Hasan al-Basri, Sufyan al-Sawri and Sa'id Jubayr as leading Sufis to confirm the conformity of their teachings with Islam. This caused asceticism to mix with Sufism. At first glance, there is a big difference between the concepts of asceticism and Sufism, and Sufis succeeded in spreading their teachings using the methods of asceticism. So, those who lived their lives with asceticism and piety, were more austere and tried not to be greedy for worldly wealth. At this point, Sufism and asceticism feel interdependence and influence. This is how views about the period of asceticism have been formed.

In the 7th-8th centuries, the ascetic life based on the fear of hell, hope for heaven, and the idea of attaining God's approval, that is, the mystical life in the form of outward worship, riyazat and mujahadas, by the 9th-10th centuries, led to the reform of the inner world of man, his purity, inner prayer, spiritual purification and It led to the idea of achieving justice as the main idea. Mystical views developed in a close and interrelated manner. Mystics began to study Sufism by researching the human psyche, changes in the soul, the stages of spiritual growth, and the ways to achieve spiritual perfection. Sufism was formed as a science in the 9th-10th centuries and began to have its own categories of concepts and principles. The views of great mystics were thoroughly studied. It was a time when many groups of mystics were formed and classic mystical works were written. During this period, the main themes of Sufism were determined.

Sufis began to appear as an independent class among members of society. In some places schools of Sufism were established. However, it should be emphasized that the term "Sufism" was in sufficient circulation in the north-eastern regions of the Arab Caliphate, but it was not widely used in Movarounnahr and Khorasan in the 9th-10th centuries. During this period, there were more discussions about asceticism in the region. After the 10th century, when ideological struggles in the Islamic world decreased a little, after Sufism became the leading doctrine of religious and mystical knowledge, not only Sufi communities, but also non-Sufi pious and learned scholars began to be called Sufis. "Al-luma fit-tasawuf" by Abu Nasr Sarraj Tusi, "Qut ul-Qulub" by Abu Talib

Muhammad Ali Atiya Harisi Makki, "Al-Ta'arruf li madhhabi ahli at" by Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Ishaq al-Bukhari al-Kalabadi. -Tasawwuf", "Risolai Qushayri", "Latoif ul-Isharat" by Sheikh Abul Qasim Qushayri, "Latoif ul-Isharat", "Kashf ul-Mahjub" by Ali ibn Usman Jullabi Hujwiri, shows that in later periods, all Sufi schools and directions were summarized under one name.

In the 9th-10th centuries, there were very favorable conditions for the development of Sufism in Movarounnahr and Khorasan, which resulted in the formation of various Sufism movements in this region. Most importantly, these schools later served as the sauce of Sufism throughout the Islamic world. Until the beginning of the 10th century, Khurasan, especially its city of Balkh, was the center of Islamic Sufism. Famous Sufis of that time, such as Ibrahim Adham, Shaiq al-Balkhi, Hatim al-Asamm, Ahmad Khazrovayh, Abu Bakr al-Warraq and Muhammad al-Fazl, were originally from Balkh, or lived and worked in this city. Many of them, such as Ahmad Khazrowaih, were connected by kinship ties with the ruling circles of the city. According to the researchers, Sufi views in Balkh were later influenced by the experiences of the Sufi schools of Movarounnahr. The currents and sects formed by the Shia and Sunni divisions in the Islamic world are sometimes differentiated.

Muhammad al-Muqaddasi (d. 380/990) in his work "Ahsan al-Taqasim" also states that during this period Sufi views were widespread in Khurasan and Mowarounnahr. It has been noted that the number of zovia, khanakah and rabots is very high in this region. Al-Muqaddasi recorded that in the second half of the 10th century, there were 1,700 rabats in Isfijab in Movarounnahr, and 1,000 rabats in Poykent. Al-Hujwiri (d. 466/1073 or 470/1077) also mentioned in his work "Kashf al-mahjub" that he met 300 Sufi mashaikhs in Khorasan, each of them had his own leeches. According to M. Kadirov, these addresses also performed the function of social protection. It also functioned as a place where orphans were given shelter and food.

In Hujviri's work "Kashf al-mahjub" it is noted that there are 12 main Sufi movements active in Khorasan in the 9th-10th centuries. These actions formed the basis for the formation of sects, some of which still exist since the end of the 11th century. Researcher Z. Narziev stated that reliable information about early Sufi sects, the names of the founders of sects, their main concepts were first studied and classified in Hujviri's work "Kashf ul Mahjub". Hujviri recognized twelve early Sufi sects, approved ten of them and criticized two of them, and explained the main concepts of these sects. In the work "Kashf ul Mahjub", ten sects are mentioned as acceptable sects, such as accounting, Kassariism-

Malamatism, Taifurism, Junaydism, Nurism, Sahlism, Hakimism, Kharrozism, Khafifism, Sayoriism. Mardud (rejected) sects are listed as Khululism and Khalajism.

The well-known orientalist O. Akimushkin said about the sects that appeared at the end of the 11th century: "Although there are many practical schools and movements that arose in the course of Sufi experiences in the history of Islam, they mainly originated from two schools. The first school is associated with the name of Abu Yazid Bistami (d. 261/875), and the second school is associated with the name of Junayd al-Baghdadi (d. 298/910). "Most of the other mystical schools and movements are derivatives of the teachings of these two schools," he says.

It can be concluded that between the 9th and 14th centuries, Sufism was formed in its own way and its theoretical system was elaborately developed. The ideas of the early Renaissance period, mystical views, religious-philosophical, mystical views developed in interdependence. The Late Renaissance fed off of the Early Renaissance. The views of mystics on Sufism and sects have developed in a variety of interactions. The formation and development of mystical views were certainly influenced by economic, social and cultural factors.

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